

Key Technology of Solar-Hydrogen Energy Systems

TOKIO OHTA

Hydrogen Energy Research Laboratories, Yokohama National University, Yokohama, Japan

Photosynthesis is the most fundamental activity for all the life on the earth. Its fundamental mechanism has a function that splits water by use of solar energy. The generated hydrogen combines with the carbon dioxide in the air and changes to biomass which is direct or indirect food for every living being. Solar hydrogen energy systems stress that the generated hydrogen should be utilised as clean and abundant energy carrier. Such hydrogen can also be raw chemical materials or clean agent for refining ones. The key technologies for such system are firstly an effective method of water decomposition using solar energy, next the transport and storage methods, and innovative utilisations. Thermodynamic fundamentals of water decomposition, direct thermal water decomposition, thermochemical cycle, and photoelectrochemical method are reviewed. Heat energy conversion and chemical heat pump by use of metal-metalhydride cycle are also briefly reviewed.

EFFECTIVE utilisations of solar energy can be summarised as follows.

(i) *Hydrogen production from water*: The value of large amount of hydrogen gas in the atmospheric circumstance is diagrammatically shown in Fig. 1. It has potencies of synthesising ammonia, producing water, and clean and powerful energy carrier. The rocket propellant for the second and third step engine systems of Saturn rocket is hydrogen. Hydrogen jet plane has also been tested². Effective hydrogen production system from water using solar energy would replace the present petroleum economy by hydrogen economy.

Fig. 1. Hydrogen in the atmosphere has a value of creating energy, fertiliser and food.

(ii) *Generation of high temperature*: Solar energy is composed of photon energy as its high quality component and heat as its low quality component. The solar heat is generated when solar beam is absorbed by materials. Thus solar heat

has usually low temperature and nothing but the entropy. However, if the collected solar beam generates high temperature, it has a high value with less entropy. Optical reflection and refraction can be used to produce high temperature easily. This is simple but a value-creation method and is never neglected in the solar energy utilisation systems. In Fig. 2, conventional methods of high temperature generation by a single concave mirror and the system combined with heliostat are shown. Theoretically we can get a temperature as high as 4 000 K. The high temperature heat generated in this way has no pollution and so clean that many applications are possible.

Fig. 2. High temperature generated by concave parabolic mirror.

(iii) *Cooperation with electric power system*: The motivation of hydrogen energy system proposal has originally come from an economical viewpoint of energy transport, that is, the energy-transportation by hydrogen from electrolysis of water by electric power is more economical than that by

high voltage electric power transmission line over a long distance. This is true in the continentals but not always valid in narrow countries such as Japan.

Another motivation of hydrogen energy system is coming from the idea of total energy system which is in cooperation with the electric power system popularised already³. This means an effectively organised energy system shown in Fig. 3. The characteristic feature of this system can be summarised as follows.

Fig. 3. Hydrogen energy system cooperating with electric energy system.

The primary energy sources are diversified, for example, solar energy as well as atomic energy are taken up. The both generate electric energy and produce hydrogen, not necessarily by water-electrolysis. Concrete examples of the hydrogen production method from water are photolysis, thermochemical cycle, and so on.

The possibility of simultaneity that produces hydrogen and generates electric power is due to the difference of appropriate temperatures between the turbine generator and the thermochemical process (for example). That is to say, the waste heat from thermochemical process has temperature high enough to motivate turbine generator.

We have two subsystems in Fig. 3, that is, the electric power system and the hydrogen energy system. These are closely related. If electric power goes to peak load, hydrogen will be converted to electric energy via fuel cell. On the contrary, the excess electric energy is stored as hydrogen via water-electrolysis. The hydrogen energy subsystem is comprised as one of the main supports in the advanced urban energy system.

Hydrogen production methods from water :

Thermodynamics of water-splitting : Total amount of energy 68.3 kcal mol⁻¹ is necessary to split water (1 mol) in liquid state under the normal condition (1 atm, 298 K) into hydrogen (1 mol) and oxygen (0.5 mol) in gaseous state at the same condition. The share of Gibbs' free energy is 56.7 kcal mol⁻¹ and the remainder (11.6 kcal mol⁻¹) is provided by heat energy. This is the reason why water-electrolysis has been the traditional and established hydrogen production system from water³.

From the thermodynamic point of view, we have⁴

$$\Delta H = \Delta G + T \Delta S \quad (1)$$

where, ΔH , ΔG , and ΔS are the changes of enthalpy, Gibbs' free energy, and entropy, respectively, when the water splits into hydrogen and oxygen at constant temperature and pressure. The second term in the right hand side of equation (1) expresses the heat energy needed in the decomposition process. At room temperature, ΔS is about 39 cal⁻¹ mol k⁻¹. The entropy change is a slowly decreasing function of temperature T.

Fig. 4 expresses the temperature dependence of entropy of water and its splitted state. The dotted line under the temperature axis shows boundary between the heat ($T \Delta S$) and the Gibbs' free energy.

Fig. 4. Enthalpy vs temperature diagram for water and its splitted state.

There are some kinds of Gibbs' free energy in our circumstance, they are photon energy, chemical energy and electrical energy. Solar hydrogen energy system has its basis upon the water-splitting system using such kind of energy coming from solar beam⁵.

Direct thermal decomposition of water : At the temperature where $\Delta G = 0$, we have

$$T^* = \Delta H / \Delta S \quad (2)$$

and the water vapour is, in principle, decomposed into hydrogen and oxygen. We can calculate the molar fractions of the splitted hydrogen and oxygen by using the partition function method⁶. An example is that the molar fraction of hydrogen in the mixed gas is 0.4 at 0.1 atm and 3 000 K.

The separation of hydrogen from the mixed gas can be done by the following ways. (i) Thin plate made of V, Nb or Pd at the temperatures as high as 900 K can pass only hydrogen molecule. (ii) Some kind of ceramics permeates only hydrogen molecule. (iii) The mixed gas is quenched

so that all kinds of gases other than hydrogen and helium are liquefied or solidified.

Thermochemical and photochemical cycles : Direct thermal decomposition of water demands the temperature as high as 3 000 K or higher. It is not always easy to provide such heat energy at rate of considerable amount being kept for hours. Therefore, it is desired to split water by heat of temperature at $\sim 1\,000$ K. This should be done with help of chemical energy (Gibbs' free energy). Such method is called thermochemical cycle and the chemical equations are, for examples,

where, A and B are the oxidating and reducing agents, respectively.

The process denoted by AB'C'D'E'F'G'H'I'DE in Fig. 4 expresses a thermochemical cycle for water decomposition. The compensation of the free energy, such as B'C', or E'F'G' are due to the released chemical energies and change in Gibbs' energy with temperature.

A typical example is the cycle which is called 'jodine-sulphur cycle'. The chemical equations are

There are many other cycles proposed and developed so far. However, selection of anti-corrosion materials at high temperatures and the difficulties in chemical engineering problems, such as products conveyance, heat transfer and so on, are not well solved yet.

Another example is a hybrid cycle which utilises heat at low temperature, photon energy, and electric energy with low voltage. All these Gibbs' free energy are generated by conversion of solar energy. This is called Yokohama Mark VII and its chemical equations (5) are

The first reaction is carried out in an aqueous state. This key reaction advances by photon energy whose wave lengths are shorter than about 6 000 Å. The third equation is electrochemical and advances applying about 0.8V.

Fig. 5 shows the systematic diagram of Yokohama Mark VII, which is a kind of precise machine utilising thoroughly solar energy. Important and difficult is the specification of photochemical cell

(P.C.C.) that produces HI and at the same time evolves O_2 by the third equation of equation (5). Vigorous efforts have been carried out to achieve this, but the need of high photon density, the separation of HI and the removal of the over-voltage of the electrolysis have still remained difficult problems.

Fig. 5. System diagram of Yokohama Mark VII. FL: Fresnel's lens, P. C. C.: photochemical cell, T. C. C.: thermochemical cell.

Photoelectrochemical decomposition of water : As early as in 1969, Honda and Fujishima have found a water splitting phenomenon by photon energy using semiconductor⁹. The experimental set-up is shown in Fig. 6. If ultraviolet beam irradiates the TiO_2 semiconductor surface, then a pair of electron (e^-) and positive hole (h^+) are generated. Electron goes to the counter electrode *via* external circuit. Positive holes react with water and evolve oxygen,

Protons migrate through the membrane to the counter electrode and recombine with electrons to make hydrogen,

This is a simple explanation of the photoelectrochemical decomposition of water. Such a water-decomposition system seems fascinating because no complex instrumentation is needed. Nevertheless electric output is also generated. However, the important and difficult point of this system lies in the choice of semiconductors. The semiconductor must satisfy the following conditions.

Fig. 6. Water decomposition system by photoelectrochemical method: (1) TiO_2 electrode, (2) Pt electrode, (3) semi-permeable membrane, (4) burette, (5) electric circuit and (6) voltmeter.

(i) Materials should not dissolve in the electrolyte. Semiconductors, such as GaP, GaAs, CdS, CdTe, CdSe are excellent for their electronic structure but soluble. In order to use these materials, one must admix S, Se, Te in the electrolyte. Ions of these admixed elements make reparation of the corroded electrode by itself. This is called the regenerative type.

(ii) Typical examples of the stable semiconductor are TiO_2 , PbO, WO_3 , SrTiO_3 . Fig. 7 shows an energy diagram describing the bottom of conduction band, the top of the valence band, H^+/H_2 level, $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{O}_2$ level and the level of vacuum. In the case of the semiconductor whose bottom of conduction band lies above the H^+/H_2 level, the water splits independently of pH value of the electrolyte. Materials such as SrTiO_3 , KTaO_3 are examples. Unless it is necessary to make difference

Fig. 7

of pH value between the both cells separated by the semipermeable membrane to give rise a bias.

(iii) Magnitude of the forbidden energy band width should be a proper value. This value must be estimated by considering the incident photon energy and the electric voltage needed to split water. One can evaluate this value to be about 2.5 eV in the case of utilising solar beam.

Heat energy conversion and storage by metal-hydride: One of the important key technologies for solar energy utilisation is how to store intermittent sunshine. Many traditional heat storage methods have been applied in this respect. However, it is almost impossible to store heat for a long period, for example, for one week. On the other hand, some kind of metals and alloys have been known as good hydrogen absorber. Among them, the following three alloy systems are typical metal-hydride^o: titanium alloy system (e.g. FeTiH), magnesium alloy system (e.g. Mg_2NiH_4) and rare earth alloy system (e.g. LaNi_5H_6). It may be seen that these metalhydrides can contain hydrogen in the interstitials of their crystal as much as in a vessel pressurised to 1 000 atm. Hydrogen storage by this system can be an important key technology in the future hydrogen energy system.

Dissociation pressure or the absorption pressure vs hydrogen to metal ratio in FeTiH is plotted in Fig. 8 at several temperatures. Such curves are called PTC characteristic.

Fig. 8. Dissociation pressure vs ratio of hydrogen atom to metal atom at some temperatures for FeTiH_x .

Another noteworthy feature of metal-metal-hydride cycle system is that the heat of reaction is evolved and absorbed reversibly, for example, we have

in the case of iron titanate. One may easily perceive that this system is conveniently applied to heat-storage for a long period. Solar heat drives out hydrogen from metalhydride, then alloy and hydrogen are stored in different vessels. Whenever heat is necessary, heat is readily generated by charging hydrogen into alloy. What is more, temperature of the generated heat can be controlled by a mechanical operation to the hydrogen pressure. This can be understood by Fig. 8.

Besides hydrogen and heat storage, this system can be applied to a heat-pump¹⁰. Such a heat-pump can be operated between high temperature source (solar heat, waste heat, etc.) and ambient temperature. This consists of two kinds of alloys having different PTC characteristic.

Heat-pump by metal-metalhydride cycle which works as heating apparatus in winter and works also as air-conditioning apparatus in summer has been widely investigated in Japan.

Closing remarks :

Solar hydrogen energy system opens a quite different economy systems from the present petroleum economy. This new energy system has two aspects. One is the hydrogen production system from water by solar energy. This field is considerably difficult in the point that calorie of generated hydrogen is much more expensive than the fossil fuels at the present stage. Another is the energy con-

version system using hydrogen as an effective energy medium. Metal-metalhydride cycle as heat-pump is an example. This system does not consume hydrogen, so that even at the present stage, the technology would replace the actual energy conversion system in near future.

Energy storage system composed of water-electrolysis and the electric power generation by hydrogen-air fuel cell is in the middle of the both mentioned above. If the hydrogen storage is carried out by metalhydride and the hydrogen is produced from water by solar energy, this will be a complete hydrogen energy system.

References

1. G. D. BREWER in "Key Technologies for Hydrogen Energy System", ed. T. OHTA, Yokohama Nat. Univ., Yokohama, 1975, p. 125.
2. T. OHTA in "Solar-hydrogen Energy Systems", ed. T. OHTA, Pergamon, Oxford, 1979, p. 1.
3. T. OHTA, J. FUNK, J. PORTER and B. TILAK, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, 1985, 10, 571.
4. T. OHTA in "Solar-hydrogen Energy Systems", ed. T. OHTA, Pergamon, Oxford, 1979, p. 25.
5. T. OHTA and T. N. VEZIROGLU, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, 1976, 1, 255.
6. S. IHARA in "Solar-hydrogen Energy Systems", ed. T. OHTA, Pergamon, Oxford, 1979, p. 59.
7. J. L. RUSSELL, JR., K. H. MCCORKLE, J. H. NORMAN, J. T. PORTER, II, T. S. ROEMER, J. R. SCHUSER and R. S. SHARPIN, "Proc. 1st. World Hydrogen Energy Conference", Miami, 1976, p. 105.
8. A. FUJISHIMA, K. HONDA and S. KIKUCHI, *J. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1969, 72, 108.
9. S. ONO, M. YAMAGUCHI and T. OHTA in "Solar-hydrogen Energy Systems", ed. T. OHTA, Pergamon, Oxford, 1979, p. 193.
10. YAMAJI, NISHIZAKI, MIYAMOTO, YOSHIDA and NAKADA in "Proc. 17th Autumn Meeting of Chem. Eng. Soc. of Japan", 1983, p. SA118.